
66. Exoplanet habitability: TESS and Gaia

SINCE THE FIRST confirmed discoveries in 1995, more than 4000 exoplanets (planets around stars other than our Sun) have been discovered. Planets, and indeed planetary systems, have been detected from the radial velocities of their host stars, with others from precise orbital timing or through gravitational lensing.

But the most prolific discovery method has been based on transit measurements, viz. measuring the temporary drop in the light from the star as a planet passes in front of its host star as seen from Earth. And of the more than 3000 transiting planets now known, the majority were discovered using NASA's Kepler satellite, launched in 2009 and operated until 2018.

Kepler focused on one region of the sky, $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ in area, and discovered planetary systems covering a large range of star and planet masses and orbital periods.

A SMALL FRACTION OF THIS remarkable haul are planets of about one to a few times the mass of the Earth, variously described as 'terrestrial', 'telluric', or 'rocky'. Detailed formation models suggest that these will be composed primarily of silicate rocks or metals, i.e. Earth-like in terms of their composition. Within our solar system, the terrestrial planets are the four closest to the Sun, i.e. Mercury, Venus, Earth, and Mars.

Unlike the larger gas and ice giants (like Jupiter and Uranus), terrestrial planets have a solid surface, and are expected to comprise a central metallic core, mostly iron, with a surrounding silicate mantle, and with typical bulk densities around $5\text{--}8\text{ g cm}^{-3}$. They may have 'secondary' atmospheres, generated through outgassing after formation, or from cometary impacts (in contrast to the giant planets, whose 'primary' atmospheres were captured directly from the original stellar nebula).

Kepler discovered several terrestrial-type planets, amongst them bodies orbiting Kepler-20, Kepler-42, and Kepler-70. But all of these, and most of the other Kepler discoveries, are in very short-period orbits around their host stars, typically with periods of less than a few days. Their scorching temperatures are considered to be totally unsuited for the development of life.

But the discovery and characterisation of exoplanets has progressed to the point where terrestrial planets are being discovered in reasonable numbers, some of which lie at star-planet separations which place them within their star's 'habitable zone'. And there is good reason to believe that such planets exist in very large numbers.

EARLY CONCEPTS of a 'habitable zone' around a star date back to Richard Bentley (1662-1742), who '*praised God's wisdom in placing our planet at just such a distance from the sun that we are neither too cold nor too hot*'. Fast forward to today, and our current assessment of the suitability of a planet for supporting life is still largely based on our knowledge of life on Earth.

With the general consensus among biologists that carbon-based life requires water for its self-sustaining chemical reactions, the search for habitable planets has focused on identifying environments in which liquid water is stable, preferably over billions of years. The presence of liquid water in turn implies that the atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature will be in ranges that promote a rich variety of organic reactions.

As of early 2022, and taking into account these and other considerations, the *Habitable Exoplanets Catalogue* lists over 20 'potentially' habitable planets, amongst them Kepler-1649, Proxima Cen, and four planets in the 7-planet system TRAPPIST-1.

IN THE SEARCH for habitable planets, and life on other worlds, two other space missions have recently joined the astronomical arsenal: as the successor to Kepler, NASA launched its Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) in April 2018. It is conducting an all-sky transit search, over an area 400 times larger than covered by Kepler, over a two-year period. It aims to survey some 200 000 solar-type stars brighter than 12 mag, hoping to discover at least 50 Earth-sized planets in the process.

And the James Webb Space Telescope, launched on 25 December 2021, targets (amongst other goals) the detailed characterisation of the atmospheres of various potentially habitable exoplanets.

AS OF EARLY 2022, TESS had discovered around 200 confirmed exoplanets, and some 5000 other candidates (NASA Exoplanet Archive). Its first, orbiting π Men, was announced in September 2018. In April 2019 came its first discovery of an Earth-sized planet, HD 21749 c, with an orbital period of about 8 days.

While TESS has observed only a fraction of the stars on its target list for long enough to be able to find Earth-mass planets orbiting Sun-like stars with orbital periods of about 1 Earth year, planets in *shorter period* orbits around *lower luminosity* stars can receive similar stellar irradiation as Earth.

It is this stellar flux, and the planet's atmosphere, which mainly determine the planet's surface temperature and therefore its possibility of maintaining liquid water. However, more detailed discussions of habitability also consider other factors, amongst them the star's spectral type, its metallicity and its ultraviolet flux, the effect of stellar flares, and tidal heating and tidal locking.

Meanwhile, it is a general principle of transit discoveries that the host star must normally be observed for a period long enough to see at least *three* transits of a candidate planet, allowing an orbit period to be estimated based on two of them, and confirmed by the third.

In this spirit, Kaltenegger et al. (2021) are maintaining the TESS *Habitable Zone Catalogue* which uses the first two years of observations to identify stars that have been observed for long enough to detect *three* transits of an exoplanet that receives similar irradiation as Earth. They used distances from Gaia DR2, along with broadband magnitudes and empirical relations, to determine the stellar luminosities, temperatures, radii, and masses.

Illustrating the importance of accurate distances, this shows the 600 brightest transiting systems known in 2018, pre-TESS (according to right ascension), with error bars indicating the uncertainty of their distances based on the 1 milli-arcsecond astrometry from Hipparcos.

The Kepler stars form the cluster of points at the lower right, at a few hundred pc distance. With the new Gaia data, distance errors are invisible on such a plot.

THEIR PRESENT CATALOGUE contains 4239 stars within 210 pc that receive similar irradiation to Earth, of which 738 are within 30 pc. While only nine are currently known to be exoplanet hosts, there are a total of 614 stars for which TESS has observed the system long enough to be able to observe planets throughout the full temperate, habitable zone out to the equivalent of Mars' orbit.

These stars, pin-pointed in space and characterised by Gaia are, they argue, amongst the best targets for discovering habitable planets from the TESS data.

FROM WHICH STAR SYSTEM would an alien observer be able to search for life on Earth?

In the same way that an exoplanet orbit must be aligned with our line-of-sight for us to observe a transit, only a subset of favourably located stars in our region of the Galaxy could see Earth as an exoplanet, transiting slowly across the face of our Sun. Our Earth's 'transit zone' is simply a band around the Earth's ecliptic plane, projected onto the celestial sphere.

This question was considered in some detail by Heller & Pudritz (2016), who suggested that any of the 10 000 G or K dwarf stars in this zone could identify Earth as habitable (and inhabited!) using the transit method.

Wells et al. (2018) found that the maximum number of transiting solar system planets that could be observed from any particular point in the sky is three. And they estimated that there are perhaps three *known* temperate Earth-sized planets orbiting G or K stars brighter than 13 mag that are located in our Earth's transit zone.

Kaltenegger & Pepper (2020) used the combination of TESS and Gaia DR2 to identify 1004 main-sequence stars within 100 pc (amongst them 77% M-type, 12% K-type, and 6% G-type), of which more than 500 are in a position to observe a minimum 10-hr long observation of Earth's transit across the face of our Sun.

And as part of its extended mission, TESS will also search for transiting planets in the ecliptic region that could already have found life on our transiting Earth!

BREAKTHROUGH LISTEN, as one part of the 'Breakthrough Initiatives', is a \$100 million program of astronomical observations and analysis, launched in 2015 and funded by the foundation established by Yuri and Julia Milner, describing itself as '*the most comprehensive ever undertaken in search of evidence of technological civilisations in the Universe*'.

In October 2019, Breakthrough Listen began a collaboration with TESS scientists to look for signs of advanced extraterrestrial life. This includes expanding Listen's original target list (adding more than a thousand 'objects of interest' identified by TESS, and aided by Gaia), and refining Listen's analysis strategy, for example, by including knowledge of planet alignments to predict when transmissions are more likely to occur.